

Neurotoxic Effects of MDMA and the Potential Neuroprotective Role of Antioxidant Supplementation: A Narrative Review and a Novel Hypothesis on Creatine*

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3,4-Methylenedioxyamphetamine (MDMA), also known as ecstasy, molly, or crys, is a psychoactive substance with therapeutic potential but also well-documented neurotoxic risks, particularly to the serotonergic system. Preclinical and clinical studies suggest that MDMA may cause long-term reductions in serotonin levels and transporter density, largely due to oxidative stress and hyperthermia. This narrative review critically analyzes existing research on MDMA-induced neurotoxicity and examines the potential protective effects of antioxidant supplementation, including alpha-lipoic acid, N-acetylcysteine, melatonin and vitamins E and C. While animal studies show promising neuroprotection, evidence in humans remains limited. Additionally, this review introduces for the first time the hypothesis that creatine supplementation could reduce MDMA-induced neurotoxicity, particularly by mitigating mitochondrial dysfunction and ATP depletion. The review discusses the validity, limitations, and implications of these findings, emphasizing the need for further research.

Keywords: MDMA, Neurotoxicity, Oxidative Stress, Mitochondrial Dysfunction, MDMA metabolites, Neuroprotection, Antioxidants, Creatine

0 INTRODUCTION

MDMA, was first synthesized in 1912 by the German pharmaceutical company Merck. It remained largely obscure until the late 1970s and early 1980s, when it gained attention among psychotherapists in the United States for its ability to enhance emotional communication during therapy sessions (Greer & Tolbert, 1998). However, by the mid-1980s, MDMA had become widely popular in recreational settings, particularly in the context of electronic dance music festivals and club culture, leading to its classification as a Schedule I substance in the United States and similarly strict control in most countries worldwide, including under the 1971 UN Convention on Psychotropic Substances.

In recent years, scientific interest in MDMA's therapeutic potential has grown. Clinical trials have demonstrated promising results in treating conditions such as

post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety associated with terminal illness, and even social anxiety in autistic adults (Mithoefer et al., 2013; Danforth et al., 2018).

However, despite its therapeutic promise, one of the principal barriers to MDMA's medical acceptance is concern over its potential neurotoxicity, particularly its impact on serotonergic neurons. Numerous animal and human studies have reported alterations in serotonin transporter density, mood disturbances, and memory deficits following high or repeated doses of MDMA (Montoya et al., 2002). These findings have significantly shaped public policy and scientific discourse, often overshadowing its clinical potential.

MDMA has been used continuously since the 1980s, but it declined considerably in subsequent years. Recently, in 2017, the EMCDDA stated that MDMA consumption and production has been steadily increasing in countries that have been surveyed since 2014. Today, in the middle of 2025, consumption has increased since then. In addition, recreational use among minors has also increased. (EMCDDA, 2017; EMCDDA, 2025)

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This essay seeks to critically review the current evidence on MDMA-induced neurotoxicity and explore whether antioxidant supplementation, including compounds like vitamin C, vitamin E, N-acetylcysteine (NAC), and alpha-lipoic acid (ALA), can offer a neuroprotective effect against such damage. There are other supplements that aid recovery from MDMA use, but this review will focus primarily on the use of antioxidants to prevent oxidative stress caused by MDMA and the hypothetical use of creatine against the mechanisms involved in MDMA toxicity.

I believe that penalizing drug use does not prevent users from harming themselves. However, if human studies were conducted on the role of these antioxidants and their effectiveness against neurotoxicity were demonstrated, it would be possible to begin to guide users on how to use them so that their use is less harmful or fatal.

If it can be robustly demonstrated that MDMA's neurotoxic effects are preventable or substantially mitigable, this could profoundly shift the ethical and scientific discussions surrounding its therapeutic use. A more nuanced understanding of these risks and their potential solutions may reopen the door for MDMA to be reconsidered as a legitimate clinical tool rather than a recreationally abused substance. If MDMA is ever approved as a treatment, it will be necessary to study which doses and conditions are therapeutic and which are neurotoxic.

1 Pharmacological Profile of MDMA

3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA) is an empathogen drug that belongs to the amphetamine family. Methamphetamine is what makes it a potent central nervous system stimulant, increasing levels of motor and cognitive activity, alertness, and attention. This methamphetamine is attached to an additional group called methyl (-CH₃). The methyl group makes the molecule more lipophilic, meaning it dissolves better in fat. This makes it easier to cross the blood-brain barrier, which allows it to enter the brain more quickly. It also increases the potency and duration of the stimulant effect, entering the brain more quickly and strongly. (Green et al., 2003; Gouzoulis-Mayfrank & Daumann, 2009).

Once in the brain, MDMA exerts its effects primarily by interacting with monoamine transporters, particularly those for serotonin (SERT), dopamine (DAT), and norepinephrine (NET). It acts as both a reuptake inhibitor and a substrate-type releaser, meaning that it not only blocks the normal reabsorption of neurotransmitters into presynaptic neurons but also enters the neuron and reverses transporter flow, causing a massive non-vesicular release of monoamines into the synaptic cleft (Rudnick & Wall, 1992; Green et al., 2003; Rothman & Baumann, 2003; Doly et al., 2009).

In particular, MDMA shows a high affinity for the serotonin transporter, where it induces reverse transport and inhibits reuptake, leading to an acute surge of extracellular serotonin (5-HT) (Rothman & Baumann, 2002). This elevated presence of serotonin causes intense activation of 5-HT receptors on postsynaptic neurons, which has been

linked to MDMA's characteristic psychoactive effects: elevated mood, emotional openness, increased empathy, sensory enhancement, and reduced anxiety (Liechti et al., 2000).

Mechanistically, the occupancy of the transporter by MDMA prevents serotonin from being taken back into the presynaptic cell, disrupting its normal recycling. This prolongs the neurotransmitter's action in the synaptic cleft and overstimulates serotonin receptors, particularly 5-HT₁ and 5-HT₂ subtypes (Green et al., 2003). Additionally, the reverse transport process leads to depletion of intracellular serotonin stores, contributing not only to the acute effects but also to the post-use comedown and long-term serotonergic toxicity associated with repeated or high-dose use (Rudnick & Wall, 1992; Scotton et al., 2019).

Thus, MDMA's neurochemical activity is both potent and complex, involving multiple mechanisms that act in synergy to create the drug's distinctive psychological profile. While the dopamine and norepinephrine systems contribute to increased energy, arousal, and locomotor stimulation, it is the massive serotonin release that underlies MDMA's unique entactogenic effects (Rothman & Baumann, 2003).

2 Mechanisms of MDMA-Induced Neurotoxicity

When we talk about neurotoxicity, it's important to distinguish between immediate and long-term adverse effects, such as serotonergic neurotoxicity. The most dangerous immediate adverse effects have been shown to be hyperthermia and dehydration. MDMA stimulates the massive release of serotonin, which disrupts the thermoregulatory system in the hippocampus. It also stimulates the sympathetic nervous system and can cause vasoconstriction, preventing heat dissipation (Mechan et al., 2002). Added to this is dehydration, due to increased sweating due to hyperthermia and increased physical activity. In addition, normal thirst and fatigue signals are suppressed and affect the response to water intake (Baggott et al., 2016). However, there are also other less serious adverse effects that some users experience, such as agitation, appetite suppression, bruxism, difficulty concentrating, dry mouth, headache, and nausea (Green et al., 2003; Moratalla et al., 2017; Costa & Gołembiowska, 2022).

When long-term effects are mentioned, they usually refer to the reduction of 5-HT and SERT, as these are the most common effects associated with MDMA use. However, other effects include anxiety, cognitive deficits, depressed mood, tolerance, and more. (Green et al., 2003; Moratalla et al., 2017; Costa & Gołembiowska, 2022).

When it comes to MDMA neurotoxicity, there seems to be a growing consensus that many of these harmful effects come from oxidative stress from free radicals. (Aguirre et al., 1999; Zhou et al., 2003). And although toxic damage to human brains is still debated, neurotoxic damage to serotonergic nerve terminals has been demonstrated in rats, guinea pigs, and nonhuman primates. MDMA neurotoxicity is complex and multifactorial, and although most studies link oxidative stress as the cause of 5-HT, DA de-

pletion and SERT reduction, there is still no firm evidence that such depletion causes cognitive impairments. (Bisagno & Cadet, 2022).

2.1 Causative Factors and Mechanistic Pathways in MDMA-Related Neurotoxicity

The consequences reported as a result of oxidative stress include lipid peroxidation, serotonin depletion, damage to monoamine transporters such as the serotonin transporter (SERT), neuroglial inflammation in response to the damage, mitochondrial dysfunction, and an increase in receptors as a compensatory response to the reduction of neurotransmitters (Montoya et al., 2002; Gudelsky & Yamamoto, 2008).

Apart from the consequences of oxidative stress, an increase in the extracellular concentration of glutamate and a reduction of the number of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) neurons in the hippocampus of rats is also stated (Anneken & Gudelsky, 2012; Anneken et al., 2016).

2.2 Oxidative Stress and Free Radical Production from MDMA

MDMA reduces serotonin levels and decreases markers such as the serotonin transporter (SERT), indicating lesions in serotonergic terminals (the final structures of neurons that are responsible for releasing the neurotransmitter serotonin, 5-HT) (Gudelsky & Yamamoto, 2008).

Multiple studies reinforce the idea that the main cause of that lesions in serotonergic terminals, and brain damage caused by MDMA, is due to free radicals. "Increasing evidence suggests that one way of MDMA-induced toxicity involves the production of reactive oxygen and reactive nitrogen species and a subsequent production of oxidative/nitrosative stress." These studies have come to this conclusion by using medications or supplements that neutralize free radicals and observing how serotonin levels and other indicators did not decrease after the effects of MDMA, which does happen when supplements are not administered. "These results further support the hypothesis that free radical formation is responsible for MDMA-induced neurotoxicity" (Aguirre et al., 1999).

MDMA triggers a massive release of neurotransmitters, such as dopamine, norepinephrine, and especially serotonin. Dopamine and norepinephrine are catecholamines, a group of substances that act as neurotransmitters and whose chemical nucleus is a catechol group and an amino group. The catechol group is chemically very reactive and prone to spontaneously autooxidize in the presence of oxygen (Green et al., 2003; Hastings, 1995).

For example, dopamine, when released into the synaptic cleft (as occurs with MDMA), can spontaneously undergo autooxidation in the presence of oxygen. Autooxidation involves dopamine donating an electron to an oxygen molecule, initiating a spontaneous redox reaction. As a result, dopamine is converted into a semiquinone, and oxygen is reduced to superoxide, which subsequently generates hydrogen peroxide and can eventually produce hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) via the Fenton reaction with

iron. The semiquinone, superoxide, and hydroxyl radical ($\bullet\text{OH}$) are reactive oxygen species (ROS) oxygen-containing molecules that are highly reactive due to the presence of unpaired or unstable electrons. Specifically, superoxide and hydroxyl radical ($\bullet\text{OH}$) are free radicals, molecules with unpaired electrons, making them extremely unstable, highly reactive, and very short-lived (milliseconds) (Sánchez-Iglesias et al., 2004; Delcambre et al., 2016; Nováček et al., 2018).

The dopamine example is just one way in which free radicals can be formed, but they can also be formed by oxidative deamination of monoamine, metabolic pathways, hyperthermia, and as we have seen, catecholamines autooxidation (Fiaschi & Cerretani, 2010).

Additionally, MDMA increases mitochondrial stress, generating more reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as superoxide and hydrogen peroxide, since mitochondria are a major source of ROS production. While moderate levels of ROS can act as signaling molecules that regulate key cellular processes, excessive ROS levels can cause damage to various cellular components (D'Autréaux and Toledano, 2007; Song et al., 2010).

2.3 Serotonin Depletion and Reduction of SERT

MDMA-induced serotonin depletion has been attributed to several interacting mechanisms. First, the drug produces a massive release of serotonin via reverse transport through the serotonin transporter (SERT), rapidly emptying presynaptic vesicular stores and leaving little neurotransmitter available for subsequent release (Hondebrink et al., 2011; Rothman Baumann, 2002). Second, oxidative stress, leads to peroxidative damage of lipids, proteins, and enzymes within serotonergic axon terminals, which impairs their ability to store and release serotonin (Huether et al., 1997).

In the process of seeking another electron to stabilize themselves, free radicals attack lipids (lipid peroxidation), destabilizing neuronal and mitochondrial membranes. They react with the polyunsaturated lipids that make up neuronal membranes, including those of axon terminals. This compromises membrane integrity, affecting both neurotransmitter release and reuptake capacity. They also attack transporters, enzymes, and ion channels essential for synaptic function. This leads to a loss of function in transporters like SERT (Farooqui Horrocks, 1998; Butterfield et al., 1999; Markesbery Lovell, 1998).

This neuronal damage caused by MDMA use is associated with a cortical reduction in SERT binding, particularly prominent in the primary sensorimotor cortex (Semple et al., 1999). In chronic MDMA users, studies have shown a significant depletion ranging from 50% to 80% in serotonin and its primary metabolite 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA) within the striatum. These findings indicate that MDMA may lead to a substantial reduction in brain serotonergic axon terminals, suggesting that some of the drug's behavioral effects could result from an acute surge followed by long-term depletion of serotonergic neurotransmission (Kish et al., 2000).

Therefore, studies suggest evidence that MDMA use causes a decrease, at least temporarily, in serotonin and SERT. This being the main reason why MDMA is considered a neurotoxic substance.

The reduction in serotonin causes an increase in the density of 5-HT_{2A} receptors. It is suggested that this increase is due to compensation for this reduction. Thus, if there were no reduction in serotonin, theoretically there should be no increase in the density of 5-HT_{2A} receptors. In recent MDMA users, significantly lower post-synaptic 5-HT_{2A} receptor densities have been observed across all cortical regions examined, whereas in former users, an increased receptor density was found specifically in the occipital cortex. These changes are thought to reflect a compensatory upregulation of 5-HT_{2A} receptors in response to persistently reduced synaptic serotonin levels (Reneman et al., 2002).

2.4 MDMA-induced mitochondrial toxicity

MDMA exerts direct harmful effects on mitochondria in both neurons and liver cells. Multiple *in vitro* studies have shown that MDMA causes marked mitochondrial dysfunction: it decreases ATP levels and inhibits complexes I and III of the mitochondrial respiratory chain (Zhou et al., 2019). This leads to collapse of the mitochondrial membrane potential and induction of mitochondrial permeability transition (MPT), which are hallmarks of mitochondrial stress (Nakagawa et al., 2017). Overall, cells exposed to MDMA display ATP depletion and reduced basal and maximal respiration, confirming that mitochondria are a critical target of the drug. These effects have been observed in both neuronal cultures and hepatocytes (for example, Zhou et al., 2019 reported inhibition of complexes I and III after exposing cells to MDMA). In some cases, respiratory inhibition depends on the concentration of MDMA used: for example, Nakagawa et al. (2017) found decreased state-3 respiration at 4 mM MDMA, whereas Custódio et al. (2010) observed no significant changes.

Generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) is central to MDMA mitochondrial toxicity. First, inhibition of the respiratory chain (particularly complex I) by MDMA increases electron leakage to oxygen, producing superoxide and hydrogen peroxide inside mitochondria. Puerta et al. (2010) demonstrated that MDMA reduces striatal complex I activity and this is accompanied by a marked increase in superoxide radical production. The authors concluded that "Inhibition of mitochondrial complex I following MDMA could be the source of free radicals responsible for oxidative stress and the consequent neurotoxicity of this drug in mice."

The brain metabolism of monoamines by monoamine oxidase (MAO) contributes to oxidative stress. MAO-B converts serotonin and dopamine into compounds that generate H₂O₂; MDMA enhances serotonin release, thereby increasing free radical formation. Alves et al. (2007) showed that inhibiting MAO-B with selegiline prevents MDMA-induced mitochondrial DNA deletions, implying

that monoamine oxidation and MAO-B-derived H₂O₂ largely accounts for the genetic damage.

These findings suggest that mitochondrial energy failure and oxidative stress lead to serotonergic terminal degeneration. Without sufficient ATP and with excess ROS, serotonergic axons cannot maintain axonal transport or protein synthesis.

Overall, MDMA creates a redox damage cycle: mitochondrial ETC inhibition elevates intramitochondrial ROS, these ROS oxidize mitochondrial proteins and DNA causing energy failure, and monoamine degradation generates further H₂O₂. These reactive oxygen species cause membrane lipid peroxidation, respiratory enzyme carbonylation, and mtDNA mutations, worsening mitochondrial failure. Chronic MDMA oxidative stress can thus trigger the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway and contribute to neuronal death.

Although MDMA has been shown to produce severe mitochondrial toxicity, most studies demonstrating toxicity use doses far higher than human recreational doses or use repeated administration protocols that do not represent clinical use or casual use. *In vitro* studies (Custódio et al., Nakagawa et al., Zhou et al.) use concentrations that are tens, hundreds, and sometimes thousands of times higher than physiological ones and are designed to demonstrate and enforce mitochondrial toxicity in the laboratory. In Puerta et al. (2010), mice were administered MDMA at 10, 20 and 30 mg/kg every two hours to assess its effects on mitochondrial electron-transport-chain complex activities, doses that, when scaled to human equivalents, far exceed what a typical recreational user would take in a single session. Therefore, at usual human doses the effects could be less severe.

2.5 Glutamate Excitotoxicity

MDMA has also been shown to produce glutamate excitotoxicity. Rats were administered 10 mg/kg of MDMA intraperitoneally every 2 hours for a total of 2 or 3 injections (20-30 mg/kg total in one day). This is higher than a typical recreational dose in humans and was delivered in a binge-like pattern that greatly amplifies neurotoxic potential. The authors reported a marked increase in extracellular glutamate in the hippocampus associated with a 36% reduction in parvalbumin-positive GABAergic interneurons in the dentate gyrus (Anneken et al., 2007).

This study represents a high dose compared to typical human use, and while it reveals potential mechanisms of neurotoxicity, it does not demonstrate that small or clinically relevant doses produce a similarly concerning increase in glutamate or GABAergic neuron loss.

3 Prevention of MDMA-Induced Neurotoxicity: Focus on Oxidative Stress and Antioxidants

Most of the available evidence on the prevention of MDMA-induced neurotoxicity comes from animal studies, primarily in rodents, and there is still a need for well-controlled human studies to determine whether such pre-

vention can be partial or even complete. In this section, the focus will be on research addressing the prevention of free radical formation and oxidative stress, mainly through the use of antioxidants. Since oxidative stress is implicated in many of MDMA's long-term effects, preventing part or all of the damage caused by free radicals could, in theory, mitigate several consequences attributed to these mechanisms, such as lipid peroxidation, serotonin depletion, damage to monoamine transporters (including the serotonin transporter, SERT), neuroglial inflammation in response to cellular injury, mitochondrial dysfunction, and compensatory receptor upregulation due to reduced neurotransmitter availability.

Although some studies have reported other potential mechanisms of neurotoxicity, these findings typically come from experiments using extremely high MDMA doses administered in patterns known to enhance toxicity. Therefore, while these effects could theoretically occur in human users, they are likely to be much less pronounced at typical recreational or therapeutic doses. Moreover, the exact causes of these phenomena are not fully understood, and it remains possible that they may also be linked, at least in part, to oxidative stress, suggesting that their severity could be reduced through antioxidant strategies.

In the following subsections, several antioxidants will be reviewed for their potential neuroprotective effects, and for the first time in this context, the use of creatine will be considered as a hypothetical intervention to reduce MDMA-induced neurotoxicity. In this context, mitochondrial dysfunction emerges as a central contributor to ATP depletion and neurotoxicity following MDMA exposure. Consequently, creatine is proposed as a bioenergetic intervention to stabilize cellular energy levels and preserve mitochondrial function.

3.1 Ascorbic Acid (Vitamin C)

In Shankaran, Yamamoto & Gudelsky (2001) it is mentioned that the neurotoxicity of MDMA on 5-HT is usually related to oxidative stress due to increased formation of hydroxyl radicals. It is mentioned that the purpose of the study is to analyze whether suppressing the formation of hydroxyl radicals with an antioxidant such as ascorbic acid attenuates 5-HT depletion and the consequences that derive from this depletion. Rats were treated with ascorbic acid (100 mg/kg, i.p. every 2 h for a total of 5 injections) and the generation of hydroxyl radicals in the striatum was suppressed during administration of a neurotoxic amount of MDMA (10 mg/kg, i.p. every 2 h for a total of 4 injections). Vitamin C was administered 1 hour before each of the four MDMA injections, and a fifth dose 1 hour after the last MDMA injection. Consequently, vitamin C was administered before and immediately after MDMA, concomitantly with the regimen. Ascorbic acid suppressed the generation of hydroxyl radicals in the striatum during administration of a neurotoxic amount of MDMA. Striatal 5-HT depletion was also attenuated. In rats exposed to a neurotoxic regimen of MDMA, the typical serotonergic response such as increased extracellular 5-HT, be-

havioral syndrome, and hyperthermia was significantly reduced. However, co-administration of ascorbic acid prevented this reduction, indicating a protective effect on serotonin system function. When rats were treated with high, repeated doses of MDMA without supplementation, a reduction in vitamin E and vitamin C was observed in the striatum and hippocampus. This decrease suggests that the brain was suffering from oxidative stress, leading to a decrease in serotonin (5-HT).

Li et al. (2006), a preliminary study, explored timing of ascorbic acid administration. The study used a single dose of MDMA 20 mg/kg (subcutaneous) to generate a long-term neurotoxicity model. Given at 5 hours post-MDMA, vitamin C (250 mg/kg), rescued cortical ATP levels, hippocampal/occipital serotonin, and SERT (serotonin transporter) mRNA expression, while also lowering GFAP expression (a marker of neuroglial inflammation). However, vitamin C given earlier (30 min before or 3 h after MDMA) did not protect these markers. When vitamin C was given at all three scheduled points in the experiment, it reduced signs of astrocyte activation/inflammation that MDMA would normally cause, it downregulate the GFAP expression.

Barbosa et al. (2012) tested 10 μ M ascorbic acid (in vitro) alongside NAC and melatonin in mouse brain synaptosomes. They observed that ascorbic acid reduced hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) generation induced by MDMA metabolites, dopamine, l-DOPA, and DOPAC evidence of its antioxidant potential at the biochemical level.

Overall, vitamin C (ascorbic acid) has shown potential in reducing MDMA-induced neurotoxicity, mainly by attenuating oxidative stress and serotonin depletion. In animal studies, it suppressed hydroxyl radical formation, reduced 5-HT loss, and preserved serotonergic function when co-administered with MDMA (Shankaran, Yamamoto, Gudelsky, 2001). Timing appears critical: post-treatment at 5 hours restored ATP, serotonin, and SERT levels, and reduced neuroglial inflammation, whereas earlier administration showed no effect (Li et al., 2006). In vitro, vitamin C reduced hydrogen peroxide formation from MDMA metabolites, supporting its antioxidant role at the cellular level (Barbosa et al., 2012). However, most evidence comes from high dose animal or cell models, and its real world applicability in humans remains uncertain.

3.2 Sodium Ascorbate and L-cysteine

Gudelsky (1996) investigated the effects of the antioxidants sodium ascorbate and L-cysteine on MDMA induced serotonergic neurotoxicity. Rats received a single subcutaneous dose of MDMA (20 mg/kg), which in untreated animals caused a 30-35% reduction in striatal serotonin (5-HT) one week later. Administration of sodium ascorbate (250 mg/kg, i.p.) or L-cysteine (500 mg/kg, i.p.) 30 minutes before and 5 hours after MDMA completely prevented this serotonin depletion. This protective effect was not related to changes in MDMA brain concentrations or its dopamine-releasing activity, supporting the hypothesis that oxidative stress plays a central role in the observed

neurotoxicity. The antioxidant doses used were pharmacological and considerably higher than typical human supplemental levels, and the findings are limited to animal models (Gudelsky, 1996). The dose of MDMA used is much higher than a recreational dose in humans, so, in normal doses, the dose of these antioxidants would also be much lower, although still much higher than recommended. This does not negate the fact that they have proven to be effective.

3.3 Melatonin

There is limited research evaluating melatonin's role in mitigating MDMA-induced neurotoxicity. One relevant example is Barbosa et al. (2012), who conducted an *in vitro* study using mouse brain synaptosomes to test several antioxidants, including melatonin, against oxidative stress induced by MDMA metabolites. They found that melatonin reduced hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) generation triggered by these metabolites, indicating antioxidant activity at the biochemical level. However, as an *in vitro* model, this work does not provide data on *in vivo* dosing, neuroprotection magnitude, or behavioral outcomes, highlighting the need for further animal and human studies to determine whether melatonin can effectively attenuate MDMA induced oxidative stress in living systems (Barbosa et al., 2012).

3.4 Vitamin E

Johnson et al. (2002) investigated MDMA administration (5 or 10 mg/kg subcutaneously, every 2 h × 4) in mice made either deficient or sufficient in Vitamin E through diet. Vitamin E deficiency significantly exacerbated MDMA-induced reductions in striatal dopamine (-47%) and elevated GFAP expression, illustrating increased vulnerability of nigrostriatal dopaminergic neurons and neuroglial activation in the absence of adequate Vitamin E. Furthermore, MDMA reduced antioxidant reserves including brain Vitamin E levels, thiols, and total antioxidant capacity and Vitamin E deficiency made hepatic necrosis more severe (especially at the 10 mg/kg dose).

Javanmard et al. (2020), investigated the protective effects of vitamin E against MDMA-induced oxidative stress in mice. Animals received 10 mg/kg MDMA intraperitoneally once daily for three consecutive days per week over five weeks, with a treatment group co-administered 150 mg/kg vitamin E via gastric gavage. Vitamin E supplementation significantly attenuated MDMA-induced hepatotoxicity, reducing serum ALT, AST, and ALP levels, restoring antioxidant defenses (GSH and SOD activity), and lowering apoptotic indices in hepatocytes. Histopathological damage, such as vacuolation, ballooning, and inflammatory infiltration, was also diminished. These protective effects were attributed to vitamin E's role as a lipid-soluble antioxidant capable of scavenging ROS, inhibiting lipid peroxidation, and modulating apoptosis pathways. While the study focused on hepatic injury, the findings support the potential of vitamin E to counteract oxidative stress mediated damage associated with MDMA exposure, a mechanism also implicated in its neurotoxic effects.

Overall, vitamin E shows strong neuroprotective and hepatoprotective potential against MDMA-induced toxicity, particularly when administered alongside the drug. Johnson et al. (2002) demonstrated that dietary deficiency of vitamin E significantly worsened neurotoxicity, with increased dopaminergic damage and glial activation. Conversely, Javanmard et al. (2020) found that coadministration of vitamin E effectively reduced oxidative stress, apoptosis, and liver damage markers. These findings suggest that adequate vitamin E levels are critical for mitigating MDMA-related oxidative injury, and its supplementation may serve as a viable strategy for preventing both neural and hepatic toxicity. However, amounts of vitamin E used here also far exceed the safe amount of supplementation a person can take on a regular basis.

3.5 N-acetylcysteine (NAC)

Soleimani Asl et al. (2013) investigated whether N-acetyl-L-cysteine (NAC) protects against MDMA-induced apoptotic signalling in the rat cerebellum. In their experiment adult male rats were treated with MDMA (reported as 2 × 0.5 mg/kg) and a second group received MDMA together with NAC 100 mg/kg *i.p.* for 7 days. Seven days after the MDMA regimen, cerebella were collected and western blots were used to quantify pro- and anti-apoptotic proteins. MDMA exposure increased the proapoptotic protein Bax and decreased the anti-apoptotic protein Bcl-2; NAC co-treatment attenuated these MDMA-induced changes (NAC reduced the Bax/Bcl-2 shift toward apoptosis), consistent with a protective, antioxidant effect on apoptotic signalling in this brain region. The authors conclude that NAC can reduce MDMA-evoked apoptotic signalling in the cerebellum (Soleimani Asl et al., 2013).

The study reports a relatively low MDMA regimen (two injections of 0.5 mg/kg each; total 1.0 mg/kg reported), which is smaller than the high "binge" dosages commonly used in many preclinical neurotoxicity models (often 5-40 mg/kg per injection or repeated high-dose regimens). Thus the MDMA exposure here is modest and closer to or below typical human-equivalent single-use ranges (a 70-kg human taking 70 mg MDMA = 1 mg/kg). By contrast, the NAC dose (100 mg/kg *i.p.*) is high compared with usual human oral NAC doses (typical clinical NAC tablets / supplements are in the hundreds to low thousands of mg total, a 100 mg/kg rat dose scales to many grams in a 70-kg human). In short: the study reports a protective effect of NAC on MDMA-induced apoptotic protein changes in the cerebellum, but the MDMA regimen used is relatively low compared with many rodent neurotoxicity paradigms, NAC was used at a high systemic dose, and the study examined a single brain region and biochemical endpoints (Bax/Bcl-2) rather than behavioural or broader neurochemical outcomes. These factors limit direct translation to humans, the data support a mechanistic antioxidant/anti-apoptotic effect of NAC in this model but further work (dose-response, different MDMA regimens, functional endpoints, and careful human-equivalent dose scaling) is required to judge therapeutic potential.

Swanepoel et al. (2017) used a “double-hit” rat model (maternal immune activation with prenatal LPS plus adolescent methamphetamine, MA) to test whether the antioxidant N-acetylcysteine (NAC) could reverse drug- and inflammation-related behavioural and neurochemical changes. Adolescents received an escalating MA regimen (0.2 - 6 mg/kg, given twice daily over 16 days), and NAC was administered thereafter at 150 mg/kg once daily for 14 days (postnatal days 51-64). NAC treatment reversed multiple adverse outcomes across the models: it normalized anxiety-like social withdrawal and recognition-memory deficits, improved prepulse-inhibition (in the combined LPS+MA group), reversed MA/LPS-associated elevations in frontal-cortical dopamine and noradrenaline, corrected several monoamine deficits (including changes in serotonin (5-HT) and DOPAC and striatal NA deficits), and attenuated markers of oxidative stress. The authors conclude that NAC was broadly effective in this preclinical model but caution against direct translational extrapolation because these are rodent, high-dose paradigms that may not map directly onto human exposure. (Swanepoel T., Möller M., Harvey B.H., 2017).

3.6 Alpha-lipoic acid (ALA)

Aguirre et al. (1999) tested whether the metabolic antioxidant Alpha-lipoic acid (ALA) prevents MDMA-induced serotonergic neurotoxicity in rats. Male Wistar rats (=220-240 g) received ALA at 100 mg/kg, i.p., twice daily for 2 consecutive days. Thirty minutes after the fourth ALA dose the animals were given a single injection of MDMA 20 mg/kg, i.p. (hydrochloride). Endpoints were assessed 7 days after MDMA administration. Methods included HPLC measurement of tissue 5-HT, [³H]paroxetine binding to estimate SERT density, and GFAP immunohistochemistry to assess astroglial reactivity. A single MDMA injection (20 mg/kg i.p.) produced the expected long-term serotonergic deficits: 40-60% decreases in tissue 5-HT content in frontal cortex, hippocampus and striatum, and 35-45% reductions in [³H]paroxetine binding (SERT density) in those regions. ALA pretreatment completely prevented the MDMA-induced reductions in 5-HT content and the loss of [³H]paroxetine binding in all examined brain areas; animals given ALA + MDMA were indistinguishable from controls on these measures. MDMA increased hippocampal GFAP immunoreactivity (reactive gliosis); ALA pretreatment fully blocked this MDMA-induced astroglial response. The results show that ALA (100 mg/kg i.p., b.i.d. for 2 days, given before MDMA) robustly prevents the characteristic MDMA-induced loss of 5-HT, SERT binding and astrocyte activation in this rodent model. Because ALA is a thiol-replenishing, redox-modulating antioxidant, the authors interpret these data as supporting an oxidative-damage mechanism for MDMA neurotoxicity and suggest that metabolic antioxidants can be protective *in vivo*.

4 Hypothesis on Creatine’s Potential Neuroprotective Role in MDMA Toxicity

MDMA has been associated with serotonergic neurotoxicity in part by disrupting mitochondrial function. In neuronal cells MDMA and its metabolites impair mitochondrial dynamics and cause calcium overload, which in turn collapse the mitochondrial membrane potential (Barbosa et al., 2014; Capela & Carvalho, 2022). This leads to inhibition of respiratory complexes I and III and a marked depletion of intracellular ATP (Capela & Carvalho, 2022). For example, Capela & Carvalho. report that MDMA causes “depletion of ATP levels and inhibition of mitochondrial complex I and III, loss in mitochondrial membrane potential, and induction of mitochondrial permeability transition”. Such energy failure is accompanied by excess reactive oxygen species (ROS) and oxidative damage (e.g. mitochondrial DNA deletion) In short, MDMA triggers an energy crisis and oxidative stress in neurons, underlying its neurotoxic effects. (Barbosa et al., 2014; Capela & Carvalho, 2022).

Creatine, via the phosphocreatine-creatine kinase system, serves as an important intracellular energy buffer that supports ATP homeostasis during metabolic stress. Through the creatine kinase system, phosphocreatine (PCr) donates a phosphate to ADP to rapidly resynthesize ATP. PCr-mediated ATP regeneration is much faster than oxidative phosphorylation, allowing cells to meet acute energy demands (Forbes et al., 2022). In neurons and glia this system helps maintain ion gradients and synaptic transmission during stress. Notably, creatine also influences calcium and redox homeostasis: sufficient creatine phosphate allows ATP-dependent Ca²⁺ pumps to function properly and “restore calcium homeostasis”. Creatine can thus help mitigate Ca²⁺ overload under certain conditions by fueling Ca²⁺ transporters, which protects mitochondria and cellular milieu. Moreover, creatine enhances mitochondrial efficiency: by shuttling ADP into mitochondria, creatine kinase activity reduces electron transport strain and lowers ROS production. Creatine supplementation can reduce markers of oxidative stress and help maintain ATP homeostasis in models of mitochondrial dysfunction; however, outcomes vary by model and dose. (Marshall et al., 2022).

Empirical studies confirm creatine’s neuroprotective capacity. *In vitro*, creatine protected neurons and glia from metabolic insults: it prevented hydrogen-peroxide-induced ATP depletion and blocked glutamate excitotoxicity. In one report, creatine “mediated a direct effect on the bioenergetic balance, leading to an enhanced cellular energy charge” and “antagonized the H₂O₂ induced ATP depletion and the excitotoxic response” (Genius et al., 2012). Similarly, creatine increased mitochondrial ATP production and reduced cell death in oligodendrocyte cultures subjected to inflammatory demyelination (Chamberlain et al., 2017). In animal and human studies, creatine intake has improved outcomes in conditions featuring oxidative stress and mitochondrial damage. For example, in models of neurodegenerative disease creatine was noted to “reduce oxidative stress, attenuate mitochondrial damage and

dysfunction, and enhance energy production through ATP resynthesis” (Forbes et al., 2022).

Given these effects, creatine may indirectly mitigate MDMA-induced neurotoxicity by counteracting the energy and oxidative crises MDMA produces. Creatine can replenish ATP rapidly when oxidative phosphorylation fails. By increasing the cellular PCr pool, creatine would help offset the ATP depletion caused by MDMA. Preserving ATP levels supports neuronal survival under MDMA stress (Capela & Carvalho, 2022). Creatine-driven ADP shuttling maintains mitochondrial phosphorylation, this may help sustain mitochondrial membrane potential and prevent the permeability transition triggered by MDMA. In other words, creatine helps “normalize mitochondrial function” during transient energy deficits (Chamberlain et al., 2017; Marshall et al., 2022). By enhancing mitochondrial efficiency, creatine lowers ROS output. Creatine supplementation has been shown to reduce ROS accumulation in models of energy failure. Thus, it could blunt the oxidative damage (mtDNA deletions, lipid peroxidation, etc.) initiated by MDMA (Marshall et al., 2022). With more ATP available, Ca²⁺ pumps can clear excess intracellular Ca²⁺. Creatine thereby “restore[s] calcium homeostasis” and attenuates Ca²⁺-mediated excitotoxic cascades that are exacerbated by MDMA. (Marshall et al., 2022).

In summary, creatine’s ability to maintain cellular energy charge and reduce oxidative stress suggests it may alleviate MDMA’s mitochondrial toxicity. While no study has directly tested creatine against MDMA toxicity, the evidence indicates that creatine supplementation bolsters ATP buffering and neuroprotection in settings of mitochondrial dysfunction. These properties could indirectly reduce MDMA-induced neurotoxicity by counteracting the ATP depletion, Ca²⁺ overload, and oxidative stress central to MDMA’s harmful effects.

5 Summary

Based on the studies analyzed, it’s important to keep in mind that most studies have been conducted on animals and may not reflect reality when extrapolated to humans. Likewise, they are very promising, and if anything has been observed, it’s that depending on the antioxidant, the timing of administration is very important to maximize its effectiveness.

Vitamin E has been shown to exacerbate the negative effects of MDMA in deficiency situations, so it’s really important to have healthy levels before consuming MDMA. It has also been shown that when administered alongside MDMA, it also reduced neurotoxicity. Therefore, it is suggested that the best time to supplement is before MDMA use, especially in deficiency situations, although it can also be effective when administered concomitantly with MDMA.

Melatonin, in this context, has only been studied *in vitro*, so it is difficult to say whether it would have any effect against MDMA neurotoxicity at normal doses. However, since it is a free radical scavenger, it is probably better to take it than not to take it, especially at bedtime.

Alpha-lipoic acid (ALA) appears to be most effective when given before MDMA, it can be effective given days before and, especially, 30 minutes before MDMA.

Ascorbic Acid (Vitamin C) appears to be most effective when given alongside MDMA, and especially 5 hours after the MDMA.

N-acetylcysteine (NAC) appears to be most effective when given alongside MDMA and also appears to reverse some damage when given for several weeks after MDMA use.

Creatine is a plausible neuroprotective candidate against the mechanisms involved in MDMA toxicity. It is usually recommended to take creatine every day, however, studies on creatine are needed in this context.

6 CONCLUSION

MDMA has therefore been shown to produce neurotoxicity. The consensus in animal studies (and indirectly supported in humans) is that MDMA’s neurotoxicity stems primarily from oxidative stress and reactive oxygen species (ROS). MDMA and its metabolites increase free radicals, and, combined with hyperthermia, this primarily damages proteins, membranes, and ultimately serotonergic axon terminals. As studies show, introducing potent antioxidants (e.g., alpha-lipoic acid, vitamin C, N-acetylcysteine) in animals effectively reduces or prevents many of the 5-HT and SERT reductions in multiple brain regions, with more limited evidence in humans. However, we do not know if supplemental doses in humans would be sufficient to block this process, because the levels of ROS generated by MDMA can exceed what peripheral antioxidants reach in the brain. Therefore, if free radicals are reduced, in theory, much of the structural damage to serotonergic terminals would be reduced, thereby preventing the reduction of 5-HT and SERT in various areas of the brain. However, certain processes would not be prevented, such as the massive release of 5-HT from synaptic vesicles, i.e., the acute depletion of 5-HT stores in neurons.

Studies indicate that MDMA carries demonstrable neurobiological risks, especially to the serotonergic system, that are mediated in large part by oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction and, under some conditions, hyperthermia and excitotoxic cascades. Preclinical work shows multiple antioxidants (vitamin C, vitamin E, alpha-lipoic acid, N-acetylcysteine and melatonin) can attenuate biochemical and histological markers of MDMA damage, but these results derive mostly from high-dose animal or *in vitro* paradigms with specific timing requirements and have limited direct relevance to routine human use. Creatine is proposed here as a novel, mechanistically plausible adjunct because it buffers ATP, supports mitochondrial function, and reduces ROS and calcium dysregulation, properties that could mitigate the energy crisis central to MDMA toxicity. However, no direct tests of creatine against MDMA exist. Translation to humans therefore requires cautious stepwise research, dose, and timing refined animal studies that mirror realistic human exposure, early-phase human pharmacokinetic/safety trials of promising agents, and

well-controlled neuroimaging/longitudinal studies in users. Meanwhile, harm-reduction priorities (dose/frequency moderation, avoiding hyperthermia/dehydration, and education) remain the most evidence-based practical measures.

7 References

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